

A COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF *JEERAKA AVALEHA* IN *RAKTAPRADARA*

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Article Received on 05 Dec. 2025,

Article Revised on 25 Dec. 2025,

Article Published on 01 Jan. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18103406>

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How to cite this Article: *¹Saniya Mahammedsab Sanadi, ²Shruthi R., ³Manasi P. S. (2026). A COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFICACY OF *JEERAKA AVALEHA* IN *RAKTAPRADARA*. World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences, 15(1), 516–526.

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ABSTRACT

Background: Raktapradara, classified under Raktapradoshaja Vikāra and described as excessive or prolonged uterine bleeding, correlates with Dysfunctional Uterine Bleeding (DUB) in modern gynecology. With hormonal therapy often limited by adverse effects and poor compliance, Ayurveda offers effective management. *Jeeraka Avaleha*, mentioned in *Yogatarangini* under Pradara Chikitsa, possesses Raktastambhaka, Pitta-sāmana and Deepana-Pachana properties, making it a promising intervention.^[15,16] **Aim:** To evaluate and compare the efficacy of Jeeraka Avaleha with Pushyanuga Choorna in Raktapradara. **Materials and Methods:** A randomized comparative clinical study was conducted on 40 patients diagnosed with Raktapradara. They were randomly divided into two groups of 20 each.

- **Group A (Trial):** Jeeraka Avaleha 24 g twice daily before food with Kṣhīra/Sukhoṣṇa Jala, from the 4th day of menstruation for 8 days, for two consecutive cycles.

- **Group B (Control):** Pushyanuga Choorna 6 g twice daily before food with Madhu and Tandulodaka, following the same schedule.

Assessment parameters included duration and interval of cycles, amount of bleeding (PBAC score, pad count), and associated symptoms. Statistical analysis was performed using Repeated Measures ANOVA on Ranks and Paired t-test and Mann–Whitney test. **Results:** Both groups showed statistically significant improvement ($p < 0.001$) in amount and duration of bleeding and associated complaints pain, irregularity, intermenstrual bleeding, clots change in odor, color etc. Jeeraka Avaleha showed faster symptomatic relief and better palatability, whereas Pushyanuga Choorna provided steady, sustained improvement in terms amount of bleeding and duration of bleeding. Intergroup comparison showed no significant difference ($p > 0.05$), indicating comparable efficacy. **Conclusion:** Both Jeeraka Avaleha and Pushyanuga Choorna are safe, effective and clinically comparable in Raktapradara. Their combined Raktastambhaka, Pitta-sāmana and Rasāyana effects support them as holistic Ayurvedic options for the management of DUB.

KEYWORDS: Raktapradara, DUB, Jeeraka Avaleha, Pushyanuga Choorna, Raktastambhana.

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, normal menstrual function depends on the balance of Doṣa, the integrity of Rasa and Rakta Dhātu, and the proper functional state of Artavavaha Srotas. Vitiating of Pitta along with Vāta leads to Rakta Duṣṭi and excessive menstrual bleeding, termed Raktapradara, which significantly impairs the physical and psychosocial health of women.^[4-6]

Suddha Artava is regarded as a key determinant of *Strī-swasthya*, and its derangement is described under *Artava-vikāra*. *Raktapradara* denotes *ati-pravṛtti* of *Raja* (menstrual blood) and is considered a *Raktapradoshaja vikāra* with predominance of vitiated Pitta and *Apāna Vāta*.^[4-6] Ācāryas have explained it mainly under *Asṛgdara*, which, by clinical presentation, closely parallels Dysfunctional Uterine Bleeding (DUB).^[7]

DUB is defined in modern gynecology as abnormal uterine bleeding in the absence of organic, systemic or iatrogenic causes.^[8,9] It is commonly associated with anovulatory cycles and contributes substantially to gynecological morbidity in the reproductive age group, leading to anemia, reduced work capacity and impaired quality of life.^[3,10-12]

Conventional management includes hormonal therapy, antifibrinolytics, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs and, in resistant cases, surgical procedures such as endometrial ablation

or hysterectomy.^[11-12] Although often effective, these measures may be costly, associated with adverse effects and unsuitable for women wishing to preserve fertility, so there is need for safer, fertility-preserving, non invasive and economical alternatives.

Ayurveda attributes *Raktapradara* to vitiated Pitta with disturbed *Apāna Vāta* and *Rakta-duṣṭi* and advocates *Nidāna-parivarjana*, *Doṣa-śamana* and *Raktastambhana–Pitta-śamana* chikitsā as the main principles of management.^[4,15,16] Among the formulations indicated in *Pradara*, *Jeeraka Avaleha* and *Pushyanuga Choorna* found to have better action. *Jeeraka Avaleha*, mentioned in *Yogatarangini* under *Pradara Chikitsā*, is described as *Raktastambhaka*, *Pitta-śāmaka*, *Balya* and *Ojovardhaka*, with ingredients such as Jeeraka, Lodhra, Nagakesara and Bala acting synergistically to control bleeding and restore strength.^[17,18] *Pushyanuga Choorna* is a classical polyherbal formulation widely used in *Pradara* for its *Kaṣāya rasa*, *Śīta vīrya*, *Grahi* and *Yonirogahara* properties, offering proven *Raktastambhana* and *Pitta-śamana* effects.^[16]

Although *Pushyanuga Choorna* is well established in the management of *Raktapradara*, *Jeeraka Avaleha* has not been adequately evaluated through comparative clinical studies. Its *Avaleha* form, palatability and *Rasāyana–Balya* profile suggest better compliance and additional benefit in women debilitated by chronic blood loss. Hence, the present study was planned as a comparative clinical trial to evaluate the efficacy of *Jeeraka Avaleha* and *Pushyanuga Choorna* in *Raktapradara* (DUB), with the aim of establishing safe, effective, non-invasive and economical Ayurvedic options for improving women's reproductive health and quality of life.

AIM OF THE STUDY

To evaluate the efficacy of *Jeeraka Avaleha* in *Raktapradara*.

OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

1. To compare the efficacy of *Jeeraka Avaleha* with *Pushyanuga choorna* in *Raktapradara*
2. To analyze haemostatic effect of *Jeeraka Avaleha* in *Raktapradara*
3. To analyze the effect of *Jeeraka Avaleha* in duration, interval and amount of bleeding in *Raktapradara*
4. To analyze the efficacy of *Jeeraka Avaleha* in the associated complaints of *Raktapradara*.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A randomized controlled comparative clinical study was conducted on **40 patients** diagnosed with *Raktapradara* fulfilling the diagnostic and inclusion criteria. Women aged **15–45 years** with excessive, prolonged or intermenstrual bleeding for at least two consecutive cycles and hemoglobin > 8 g/dL were included. Patients with bleeding disorders, thyroid dysfunction, PCOS, IUCD/OCP use, pelvic infections, fibroids, polyps, endometriosis, adenomyosis or any structural uterine pathology were excluded.^[1-3]

Study Design and Sampling

Eligible patients were selected from the outpatient and inpatient departments of Ayurveda hospitals.

Intervention

They were randomly allocated into two groups of **20 patients each**

- **Group A:** Jeeraka Avaleha, **24 g twice daily**, before food, with *Kṣīra* as *Anupāna*, from the 4th day of menstruation for **8 days**, repeated for **two consecutive cycles**.
- **Group B:** Pushyanuga Choorna, **6 g twice daily**, before food, with *Madhu* and *Tandulodaka*, in the same schedule.

Assessment Criteria

Patients were assessed on subjective and objective parameters:

- **Duration of menstrual flow**
- **Amount of blood loss** (PBAC scoring)
- **Interval between cycles**
- **Pain during menstruation**
- **Intermenstrual bleeding**

Scoring was done using standard grading scales for each parameter. Overall therapeutic response was classified as marked, moderate, mild or unchanged improvement based on percentage relief in symptoms.

Study Duration and Follow-up

Treatment was administered for **two consecutive menstrual cycles**. Follow-up assessment was conducted during the **third cycle** to evaluate sustained effect.

Investigations

Baseline and post-treatment investigations included **Hb%, CT, BT, thyroid profile and pelvic ultrasonography** to rule out secondary causes of abnormal bleeding.^[8-11]

Ethical Considerations

The study received approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee, and all patients provided informed consent. The trial is registered under **CTRI/2024/09/073661**.

Statistical Analysis

Data was analyzed using appropriate statistical tests, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Baseline Profile

Forty patients of *Raktapradara* were randomized into two groups of 20 each:

- **Group A:** Jeeraka Avaleha
- **Group B:** Pushyanuga Churna

Majority were **25–29 years (27.5%)**, married (62.5%), and housewives (52.5%). Most were from **rural areas (60%)** and middle socioeconomic class (60%). **BMI:** 67.5% normal, 17.5% overweight, 12.5% underweight, 2.5% obese. **Prakṛti:** Vāta–Pittaja predominant (60%). Clinically, **52.5%** had **irregular cycles**, **52.5%** had **>9 days bleeding**, 45% had **moderate PBAC (150–199)**, 50% had **moderate pain**, and most had mildly reduced Hb (11.1–12 g/dL in 72.5%). Baseline parameters were comparable between groups.

Effect on Duration and Amount of Bleeding- Within-group (both): Both Jeeraka Avaleha and Pushyanuga Churna produced **highly significant reduction** in: **Duration of bleeding** from the 2nd cycle onwards, sustained at follow-up. **Amount of bleeding (PBAC)** with >50% reduction after the 2nd cycle and maximum improvement at follow-up. **Intergroup:** No **statistically significant difference** between the two groups for duration or amount of bleeding; thus, both were **equally effective hemostatically**.

Effect on Pain - Group A (Jeeraka Avaleha): Rapid and consistent reduction in pain with ≈40% relief after 1st cycle, ≈68% after 2nd, and ≈89% at follow-up; all changes **highly significant**. **Group B (Pushyanuga Churna):** Mild, non-significant change after 1st cycle; **significant improvement** from 2nd cycle onwards; ≈61% relief at follow-up. **Intergroup:**

Jeeraka Avaleha showed significantly better and faster pain relief than Pushyanuga Churna.

Other Parameters Both groups showed **clinical improvement** (though mostly statistically non-significant) in: Cycle regularity and interval, Colour of menstrual blood (towards normal), Odour and clots (reduced/absent), Intermenstrual bleeding (reduced in affected few). Improvements were comparable between groups.

Overall Effect of Therapy

Response Category	Criteria (% Improvement)	Group A – Jeeraka Avaleha (%)	Group B – Pushyanuga Churna (%)
Marked response	76–100%	60	50
Moderate response	51–75%	35	40
Mild response	26–50%	5	10
Total	—	100	100

No poor responders in either group. Both drugs were **effective and comparable** in *Raktapradara*, with **Jeeraka Avaleha** showing **marginal superiority and faster symptomatic relief**, especially for pain.

DISCUSSION

Raktapradara is a Rakta–Pitta-pradhāna condition with Apāna Vāta involvement, characterized by excessive or prolonged uterine bleeding. Classical texts equate it with Asṛgdara, arising from vitiation of Rakta Dhātu and Artavavaha Srotas. also pradara is an upadrava of yonivyapad. In modern gynecology, it corresponds to Dysfunctional Uterine Bleeding (DUB), a diagnosis of exclusion resulting from HPO axis dysregulation and endometrial instability.

Conceptual Background

Artava, an *Upadhātu* of **Rasa Dhātu**, is governed by **Jatharāgni** and **Rasadhātvaṅni**. **Agnimāndya** due to **Ahāra–Vihāra doṣa** and **Manasika nidāna** leads to **Apakva Rasa utpatti**, resulting in **Rasa–Rakta Dhātu duṣṭi** and **Artava-vikṛti**, thereby disturbing the normal **Ritupravṛtti** of menstruation.^[4,17]

Predominant **Pitta prakopa** (Uṣṇa, Drava) causes **Rakta vṛddhi** and **Ati-pravṛtti** of **Rakta**, while associated **Apāna Vāta duṣṭi** (Chala, Pravāha) produces **Nīyantraṇa-hāni** of **Adhoga**

pravṛtti, leading to excessive and prolonged Raja srava. **Kapha Doṣa**, through its **Guru** and **Snigdha guṇa**, induces **Srotorodha** and **Śleṣma sañcaya** in the **Garbhaśaya**, resulting in **Asamyak chedana of Artava** and persistence of bleeding.^[4,17]

Thus, **Pitta-pradhāna Tridoṣa duṣṭi**, **Rasa–Rakta Dhātu duṣṭi**, **Artava-vikṛti**, and **Artavavaha Srotodushti (Ati-pravṛtti)** together manifest as **Raktapradara (Asṛgdara)**.

DRUG DISCUSSION

Jeeraka Avaleha

Jeeraka Avaleha contains Deepana–Pachana, Raktastambhaka, and Pitta–Kapha Śāmaka dravyas such as Jeeraka, Mustā, Pippalī, Haridrā, and Lodhrā. With predominance of Laghu and Uṣṇa guṇa and Kaṭu–Tikta rasa, it corrects Agnimāndya and regulates Rasa–Rakta Dhātu formation. The Ghṛita–Kṣīra–Śarkarā base imparts Rasāyana and Dhātu-puṣṭikara effects, supporting Garbhaśaya balya and facilitating effective control of Ati-pravṛtti of Raja in Raktapradara.^[15,16]

Pushyanuga Choorna

Pushyanuga Chūrṇa contains Kaṣāya rasa and Śīta vīrya dravyas such as Lodhra, Pāṭhā, Mustā, Dhātakī, Gairika, and Raktacandana. With predominance of Laghu and Rūkṣa guṇa, it exhibits Grahi and Stambhaka karma, leading to Rakta-sañgrahaṇa and regulation of Ati-pravṛtti of Raja. Its Śīta vīrya facilitates Pitta-śamana and Rakta-praśamana, thereby supporting Garbhaśaya sthīrīkaraṇa and sustained control of bleeding in Raktapradara.^[4,16]

Probable Mode of Action

1. Hemostatic Effect (Raktastambhana)

- **Jeeraka Avaleha:** Lodhra, Rasaja, Vamsalocana contain tannins and polyphenols that enhance vasoconstriction and promote platelet aggregation.
- **Pushyanuga Choorna:** Lodhra, Gairika, Mocharasa and Dhataki possess strong astringent properties that reduce vascular fragility and capillary permeability.

Outcome: Significant reduction in volume and duration of bleeding.

2. Agni Deepana & Srotoshodhana

- **Jeeraka Avaleha:** Jeeraka, Pippali and Śuñṭhī enhance Agni, reduce Āma, regulate Rasa–Rakta production and ensure proper biochemical transformation.^[16]

- **Pushyanuga Choorna:** Musta and Patha improve metabolic processing and clear Srotas, aiding hormonal rhythm and endometrial stability.^[16]

Outcome: Improved hormonal signaling, better cycle regularity and reduced bleeding abnormalities.

3. Endometrial Repair (Rasāyana & Balya Action)

- **Jeeraka Avaleha:** Bala, Draksha, Kṣīra and Ghṛita provide Dhātu-pushti and support quick endometrial regeneration and tissue healing.^[16]
- **Pushyanuga Choorna:** Madhuka, Arjuna and Dhataki strengthen uterine musculature, enhance tissue integrity and promote healthy endometrial shedding.^[16]

Outcome: Faster recovery, improved endometrial architecture and reduced recurrence.

4. Hormonal Modulation

- **Jeeraka Avaleha:** Balances Apāna Vāta and Pitta, supporting estrogen-progesterone equilibrium and cyclical shedding.^[13,22]
- **Pushyanuga Choorna:** Reduces Rakta–Pitta dushti, stabilizes endometrial turnover and normalizes bleeding pattern.^[13,20]

Outcome: Restoration of cyclical rhythm and normalization of menstrual function.

5. Anti-inflammatory & Analgesic Effects

- **Jeeraka, Haridra, Pippali, Musta** reduce pelvic congestion, prostaglandin-induced cramping and uterine inflammation.^[16]
- **Raktachandana and Patha** in Pushyanuga Choorna reduce endometrial inflammation and burning sensations.^[16,20]

Outcome: Significant relief of dysmenorrhea and pelvic discomfort.

DISCUSSION ON STUDY RESULTS

Duration & Amount of Bleeding

Both interventions showed highly significant improvement (**p < 0.001**).

- **Jeeraka Avaleha:** ~89% reduction in duration, 72% reduction in PBAC score.
- **Pushyanuga Choorna:** ~79% reduction in duration, 45% reduction in PBAC score.

Jeeraka Avaleha acted faster due to its systemic Vāta-Pitta balancing and Agni-Deepana profile.

Cycle Interval & Regularity

Both groups showed improvement, with Jeeraka Avaleha demonstrating quicker normalization owing to enhanced Apāna Vāta regulation and Agni correction.

Pain (Dysmenorrhea)

- **Jeeraka Avaleha:** 89% improvement.
- **Pushyanuga Choorna:** 61% improvement.

This difference corresponds to the stronger anti-inflammatory and analgesic actions of Jeeraka Avaleha ingredients.

Clots, Colour, Odour

Both groups showed clinical improvements—indicating better Rakta quality, reduced Pitta dushti and physiologic endometrial shedding.

Intermenstrual Bleeding (IMB)

IMB resolved completely (100%) at follow-up in both groups.

Overall Response

- **Jeeraka Avaleha:** 95% moderate–marked improvement.
- **Pushyanuga Choorna:** 90% moderate–marked improvement.

The superior palatability of Jeeraka Avaleha enhanced patient compliance, resulting in a more rapid therapeutic response.

Both Jeeraka Avaleha and Pushyanuga Choorna are clinically effective in Raktapradara through combined **Raktastambhana, Deepana-Pachana, Rasāyana, Pitta-Vāta Shamamana and endometrial-repair mechanisms**, correlating well with modern DUB pathology. Jeeraka Avaleha offers faster symptomatic relief, while Pushyanuga Choorna shows steady, sustained action.

Drawbacks and Study Difficulties

The study was limited by a small sample size and a short follow-up period, which restricted the assessment of long-term efficacy and recurrence. Additionally, the comparatively short shelf life of Jeeraka Avaleha posed challenges with respect to storage and large-scale applicability; hence, development of Jeeraka Avaleha in granule form may offer improved shelf stability and wider clinical usability.

CONCLUSION

The present comparative clinical study demonstrated that **Jeeraka Avaleha** and **Pushyanuga Choorna** are both **safe, effective, and clinically comparable** in the management of **Raktapradara (DUB)**. Both groups showed **highly significant improvement** in the **duration and amount of bleeding**, along with marked relief in **pain, irregularity of cycles, and intermenstrual bleeding**.

Jeeraka Avaleha provided **faster symptomatic relief** with better palatability and patient compliance, whereas Pushyanuga Choorna exhibited **steady and sustained hemostatic action** throughout follow-up. Statistical analysis revealed **no significant intergroup difference ($p > 0.05$)**, confirming **clinical equivalence**, and supporting the **Null Hypothesis**.

The therapeutic efficacy of both formulations can be attributed to their **Raktastambhaka, Pitta-Shamana, Deepana–Pachana, and Rasayana** properties, which collectively restore **Dhatu Samyata**, enhance **uterine tone**, regulate **Apāna Vāta**, and support **endometrial repair**.

Overall, the study validates these classical Ayurvedic formulations as **holistic, dependable, and effective** options for the management of **Raktapradara / Dysfunctional Uterine Bleeding (DUB)**.

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